

INTEGRATING RESPONSIBLE AI IN ABUSE HELPLINE CONTACT CENTERS: A FRAMEWORK FOR ETHICAL IMPLEMENTATION AND HUMAN-CENTERED SUPPORT

Santhosh Kumar Ganesan

Microsoft, USA

ABSTRACT

This article examines the integration of Artificial Intelligence (AI) technologies in abuse helpline contact centers, presenting a comprehensive framework for ethical implementation that prioritizes technological innovation and human-centered support.

The article identifies critical considerations in AI deployment, analyzing existing literature and operational case studies, including privacy protection, bias mitigation, and emotional intelligence integration. The article establishes a novel human-AI collaboration model that emphasizes AI as a supportive tool rather than a replacement for human operators, incorporating real-time assistance capabilities while maintaining essential human oversight. Our article demonstrates that successful implementation requires a carefully balanced approach incorporating four key elements: (1) robust ethical guidelines for data handling and decision-making transparency, (2) clear protocols for AI-human collaboration that preserve the primacy of human empathy, (3) comprehensive safety and accountability measures, and (4) adaptable frameworks for emotional intelligence integration. The article concludes with practical recommendations for implementation, addressing regulatory compliance, training requirements, and quality assurance measures. These findings contribute to the growing body of literature on responsible AI implementation in sensitive support services while providing actionable insights for organizations seeking to enhance their abuse helpline operations through technological innovation without compromising the human-centered nature of crisis support.

Keywords: Responsible Artificial Intelligence, Crisis Support Services, Human-AI Collaboration, Digital Ethics, Contact Center Technology.

Cite this Article: Santhosh Kumar Ganesan, (2024). Integrating Responsible AI in Abuse Helpline Contact Centers: A Framework for Ethical Implementation and Human-Centered Support. *International Journal of Research in Computer Applications and Information Technology*, 7(2), 1026–1042.

https://iaeme.com/MasterAdmin/Journal_uploads/IJRCAIT/VOLUME_7_ISSUE_2/IJRCAIT_07_02_080.pdf

I. INTRODUCTION

The digital transformation of crisis support services, particularly abuse helplines, represents a critical intersection of technological innovation and humanitarian aid. As contact centers worldwide face increasing demand and complexity in support requests, integrating Artificial Intelligence (AI) offers promising solutions for enhancing service delivery while maintaining human-centered care. However, the sensitive nature of abuse helpline operations presents unique challenges in AI implementation, requiring careful consideration of ethical implications, privacy concerns, and the preservation of human empathy. Hagendorff's comprehensive analysis of AI ethics guidelines highlights the critical importance of establishing robust ethical frameworks when deploying AI in sensitive contexts, particularly emphasizing the need for human oversight and value-sensitive design [1]. Building upon these foundational principles, there remains a significant gap in understanding how to effectively and responsibly implement AI technologies specifically within abuse helpline contexts. This article addresses this gap by developing a comprehensive framework for ethical AI integration in abuse helpline contact centers, emphasizing the critical balance between technological advancement and human-centered support. The article examines key considerations in responsible AI deployment, including privacy protection, bias mitigation, and emotional intelligence integration, while establishing clear protocols for human-AI collaboration that preserve the essential human element of crisis support.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

A. Current State of Abuse Helpline Services

Historically, traditional abuse helpline services have operated through voice-based communication channels, relying heavily on trained human operators to provide immediate crisis support and intervention. These operational models typically follow a three-tier structure: initial contact and triage, immediate support provision, and referral to specialized services. The existing technological infrastructure in most abuse helplines centers around traditional telephony systems integrated with basic customer relationship management (CRM) tools, which often struggle to handle increasing call volumes and maintain consistent service quality. Common limitations include extended wait times, operator burnout, inconsistent service delivery, and challenges in providing multilingual support.

The current technological framework faces several critical challenges. Data from recent studies indicates that helpline services require significant technological transformation to meet growing demands while maintaining service quality [2]. These limitations are particularly evident in:

- Queue management during high-volume periods
- Real-time language translation capabilities
- Consistent quality assurance monitoring
- Comprehensive data collection and analysis
- Integration of multiple communication channels

B. Artificial Intelligence in Support Services

The evolution of AI in contact centers represents a significant shift from basic rule-based automation to sophisticated, context-aware support systems. Modern AI applications in support services encompass natural language processing (NLP), sentiment analysis, and predictive behavioral modeling, fundamentally transforming how contact centers operate and deliver services. These technologies have demonstrated particular promise in:

- Automated triage and priority assignment
- Real-time conversation analysis
- Multilingual support capabilities
- Pattern recognition in crises
- Predictive resource allocation

Implementing AI technologies in support services has shown measurable improvements in service delivery metrics [3]. Successful case studies have demonstrated that AI-augmented support services can effectively:

- Reduce wait times while maintaining service quality
- Improve consistency in service delivery
- Enhance data collection and analysis capabilities
- Support operators with real-time insights
- Facilitate more effective resource allocation

Component	Primary Function	Key Considerations
Emotion Detection Systems	Pattern recognition, Risk assessment, Urgency evaluation	Privacy protection, Cultural sensitivity, Accuracy levels
Decision Support Tools	Resource allocation,	Human oversight,

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	Response suggestion, Protocol adherence	Transparency, Accountability
Integration Infrastructure	System connectivity, Information flow, Service continuity	Data security, Interoperability, Scalability

Table 1: AI System Components in Crisis Support Services [1, 2, 3]

III. ETHICAL FRAMEWORK FOR AI IMPLEMENTATION

A. Privacy and Confidentiality Considerations

Implementing AI in abuse helpline services demands rigorous adherence to privacy and confidentiality standards that exceed typical data protection requirements. Building upon established model card frameworks, the privacy considerations must be documented and implemented systematically, addressing both technical and ethical dimensions of data protection [4]. Contemporary approaches to data protection in AI-enabled support systems implement multi-layered security protocols, including:

- End-to-end encryption for all communications
- Segregated data storage architectures
- Real-time data anonymization pipelines
- Automated PII (Personally Identifiable Information) detection and redaction
- Granular access control mechanisms

Secure information storage protocols, as outlined in standardized model reporting frameworks, have evolved to incorporate:

- Differential privacy implementations
- Federated learning approaches
- Homomorphic encryption for data processing
- Dynamic pseudonymization
- Temporal data degradation

B. Bias Mitigation Strategies

The model cards framework provides a structured approach to addressing bias in AI systems for crisis support, emphasizing comprehensive documentation and testing of:

- Demographic representation across multiple dimensions
- Linguistic and cultural variation
- Situational diversity in crisis scenarios
- Temporal distribution of cases
- Geographic representation

Bias detection methodologies, following the model cards structure, employ multiple approaches:

- Automated fairness metrics monitoring
- Cross-demographic performance analysis
- Regular bias audit procedures
- Intersectional testing frameworks
- Continuous feedback loop integration

The framework establishes ongoing monitoring and correction procedures through:

- Real-time bias detection systems
- Dynamic model retraining protocols
- Regular fairness assessments
- Stakeholder feedback integration
- Continuous performance monitoring across demographic groups

C. Transparency in AI Operations

Transparency requirements, as specified in the model cards framework, focus on three core areas: decision-making visibility, comprehensive documentation, and stakeholder communication. The decision-making transparency framework includes:

- Explainable AI implementations
- Clear decision path logging
- Human-readable justification generation
- Intervention point identification
- Outcome tracking and validation

Documentation requirements, following model card specifications, encompass:

- Detailed model architecture specifications
- Training data characteristics and sources
- Performance metrics and limitations
- Update and maintenance procedures
- Incident response protocols

Stakeholder communication protocols ensure:

- Regular performance reporting
- Incident notification procedures
- User-friendly explanation systems
- Feedback collection mechanisms
- Continuous improvement documentation

IV. HUMAN-AI COLLABORATION MODEL

A. Complementary Roles

The effective integration of AI in abuse helpline environments demands a carefully structured collaboration model that enhances rather than replaces human capabilities. AI support functions are designed to augment human operators' abilities through intelligent assistance while preserving the critical human elements of crisis support. Building upon established frameworks for human-AI collaboration [5], the system defines specific roles and responsibilities for each component:

AI Support Functions:

- Automated initial risk assessment
- Real-time conversation summarization
- Resource recommendation systems
- Pattern recognition in crisis indicators
- Multilingual translation support
- Documentation automation

Human Operator Core Responsibilities:

- Emotional support and empathy provision

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- Complex situation assessment
- Critical decision-making
- Intervention strategy development
- Relationship building
- Ethical judgment calls

Integration points and workflows are structured to ensure seamless collaboration:

- Clear handoff protocols between AI and human operators
- Defined escalation pathways
- Feedback loops for continuous improvement
- Quality assurance checkpoints
- Performance monitoring systems

Fig. 1: Task Distribution in Crisis Support Centers [5]

B. Real-time Support Systems

Implementing real-time support systems focuses on enhancing operator effectiveness through advanced AI capabilities. Modern sentiment analysis applications in crisis support contexts provide:

- Emotional state detection
- Urgency level assessment
- Risk factor identification
- Tone analysis
- Behavioral pattern recognition

Language processing capabilities have been enhanced to support crisis communication through:

- Natural language understanding
- Context-aware response suggestion
- Cultural nuance detection

- Linguistic pattern analysis
- Semantic relationship mapping

Intervention triggers and protocols are established based on:

- Risk level thresholds
- Behavioral indicators
- Language pattern analysis
- Historical case comparison
- Real-time escalation metrics

Key intervention protocols include:

- Automated alert systems
- Gradual escalation pathways
- Emergency response triggers
- Supervisor notification workflows
- Resource mobilization procedures

V. SAFETY AND ACCOUNTABILITY FRAMEWORK

A. Deployment Safety Measures

Implementing AI systems in crisis support services requires comprehensive safety measures that ensure reliable and responsible deployment. In abuse helplines, where system failures could have severe consequences for vulnerable individuals, traditional software testing approaches must be augmented with specialized protocols for AI systems [6]. The criticality of these services demands a zero-tolerance approach to system failures, particularly in scenarios involving high-risk crises.

Testing Protocols have evolved to address the unique challenges of AI in crisis support:

- Unit testing of AI components, with particular attention to edge cases in crisis scenarios
- Integration testing with existing systems to ensure seamless handoffs
- End-to-end system validation under various stress conditions
- Adversarial testing scenarios that simulate worst-case situations
- Load and stress testing to ensure performance under peak demand
- Recovery testing protocols for system resilience

Risk Assessment Methodologies have been specifically adapted for crisis support contexts, incorporating:

- Systematic hazard identification through scenario modeling
- Failure mode and effects analysis with emphasis on user safety
- Probability impact matrices for risk prioritization
- Contingency planning for various failure scenarios
- Risk mitigation strategies with redundant safety measures
- Regular risk reassessment cycles to address emerging threats

Performance Monitoring Systems are designed for proactive intervention, utilizing:

- Real-time performance metrics with automated alerts
- Error rate tracking across different types of interactions
- Response time monitoring for critical situations
- System reliability measures with emphasis on availability
- Accuracy assessment tools for AI recommendations
- Automated alert systems for performance degradation

B. Human Oversight Integration

The integration of human oversight represents a critical safeguard in AI-enabled crisis support systems. Experience has shown that even well-designed AI systems can occasionally make unexpected decisions, making human supervision essential. The framework establishes comprehensive supervision protocols:

- Real-time monitoring capabilities with immediate intervention options
- Clearly defined escalation pathways for different risk levels
- Intervention thresholds based on empirical evidence
- Oversight responsibility matrices with clear accountability
- Emergency override procedures for immediate human control
- Regular supervisory reviews of AI decisions

Decision Review Processes are structured to ensure continuous learning and improvement:

- Systematic decision auditing with a focus on high-risk cases
- Performance evaluation metrics aligned with service objectives
- Outcome analysis protocols to identify improvement areas
- Error investigation procedures with root cause analysis
- Corrective action tracking through completion
- Learning feedback loops for system enhancement

Quality Assurance Measures incorporate both automated and human elements:

- Regular system audits with standardized protocols
- Performance benchmarking against established standards
- User satisfaction monitoring through multiple channels
- Service level agreement tracking with automated alerts
- Compliance verification with relevant regulations
- Continuous improvement processes based on feedback

VI. REGULATORY COMPLIANCE AND GOVERNANCE

In the rapidly evolving landscape of AI-enabled crisis support services, regulatory compliance, and governance have become increasingly complex and critical. The intersection of sensitive personal data, crisis intervention, and automated systems creates unique challenges that demand robust frameworks and vigilant oversight [7]. The dynamic nature of both technology and regulations requires organizations to adopt flexible yet comprehensive approaches to compliance.

A. Legal Requirements

The regulatory landscape for AI-enabled crisis support services reflects an intricate web of overlapping requirements designed to protect vulnerable individuals while enabling effective service delivery.

Data Protection Standards have evolved beyond simple privacy measures:

- GDPR compliance mechanisms have become increasingly sophisticated, incorporating:
 - Data minimization protocols that balance service quality with privacy
 - Purpose limitation frameworks ensuring data use aligns with user consent
 - Storage limitation policies that consider both immediate needs and long-term support
 - Data subject rights management systems that empower users while protecting their interests

Mandatory Reporting Obligations present unique challenges in AI-enabled environments:

- Immediate threat protocols must balance automation with human judgment
 - Suicide risk reporting requires nuanced assessment capabilities
 - Abuse disclosure handling demands careful documentation and swift action
 - Minor protection requirements necessitate specialized handling protocols
- Legal documentation requirements have adapted to include AI-specific considerations
 - Chain of custody maintenance for AI-processed information
 - Evidence preservation protocols that account for automated decision-making
 - Audit trail management capturing both human and AI interactions

Service Accessibility Requirements have expanded to encompass:

- Universal access provisions that consider technological barriers
 - Multi-language support with cultural sensitivity
 - Disability accommodation that accounts for AI interaction patterns
 - Technical accessibility standards for AI-enhanced interfaces

B. Monitoring and Updates

Integrating AI systems has transformed how organizations approach compliance monitoring and system updates. Modern frameworks recognize that static compliance measures are insufficient in dynamic environments.

Compliance Tracking Systems have evolved to provide:

- Real-time monitoring capabilities that detect:
 - Potential compliance violations before they occur
 - Patterns that might indicate emerging risks
 - Opportunities for process improvement
- Performance metrics that consider both technical and human factors
 - Response time analytics across different crisis categories
 - Service quality indicators that incorporate AI performance
 - Accessibility compliance verification through automated tools

Update Protocols reflect the need for continuous adaptation:

- System updates must balance security with service continuity
 - Careful testing of AI model updates
 - Staged rollouts to minimize risk
 - Emergency rollback procedures
- Change management processes that consider:
 - Impact on crisis support effectiveness
 - Training requirements for human operators
 - Documentation updates for compliance purposes

Documentation Requirements have become more comprehensive:

- Record keeping must capture:
 - AI decision processes and human oversight
 - System changes and their justifications
 - Incident responses and outcomes
- Reporting procedures need to address:
 - Multiple stakeholder requirements
 - Various regulatory frameworks

- Internal improvement processes

VII. EMOTIONAL INTELLIGENCE INTEGRATION

The integration of emotional intelligence in AI-assisted crisis support represents a critical advancement in mental health services [8]. Drawing from foundational work in affective computing, modern crisis support systems must balance technological capabilities with human empathy, ensuring that AI augments rather than replaces human emotional understanding.

Component	Capabilities	Implementation Metrics
Pattern Recognition	Sentiment analysis, Emotion detection, Crisis indicators	Accuracy rate, Response time, Cultural sensitivity
Behavioral Analysis	Communication patterns, Risk assessment, Usage monitoring	Pattern accuracy, Alert precision, False positive rate
Context Processing	Situation assessment, Cultural interpretation, Risk evaluation	Context relevance, Adaptation rate, Error margin

Table 2: Emotional Recognition System Components [8]

A. Emotional Recognition Systems

The implementation of emotional recognition in crisis contexts demands sophisticated approaches that go beyond basic sentiment analysis. Modern systems must operate with high precision while maintaining sensitivity to the nuanced nature of emotional expression during crises.

Detection Capabilities have evolved to include:

- Multi-modal Analysis
 - Textual emotion recognition
 - Voice pattern analysis
 - Behavioral marker detection
 - Context Interpretation
- Real-time Processing
 - Immediate emotion assessment
 - Dynamic state tracking
 - Pattern recognition
 - Risk level evaluation

Response Protocols emphasize safety and effectiveness:

- Systematic Assessment
 - Initial risk evaluation
 - Ongoing monitoring
 - Threshold detection
 - Alert generation
- Adaptive Responses
 - Context-sensitive actions
 - Personalized approach

- Cultural adaptations
- Age-appropriate interactions

Handoff Procedures ensure seamless support:

- Transition Management
 - Clear handoff triggers
 - Information continuity
 - Context preservation
 - Support maintenance
- Emergency Protocols
 - Crisis escalation paths
 - Immediate response procedures
 - Resource mobilization
 - Team coordination

B. Empathetic Response Framework

Building on Picard's work in affective computing, the empathetic response framework establishes structured approaches for AI systems to provide appropriate emotional support while recognizing their limitations.

Response Design Principles incorporate:

- Human-Centered Design
 - Empathy-first approach
 - User experience focus
 - Ethical considerations
 - Safety prioritization
- Evidence-Based Practices
 - Validated methodologies
 - Outcome monitoring
 - Effectiveness assessment
 - Continuous refinement

Language Guidelines ensure appropriate communication:

- Contextual Adaptation
 - Situation-appropriate tone
 - Cultural sensitivity
 - Age-appropriate language
 - Crisis-aware vocabulary
- Communication Structure
 - Clear message delivery
 - Supportive phrasing
 - Trauma-informed language
 - Safety-focused dialogue

Escalation Protocols maintain safety:

- Risk Assessment
 - Continuous monitoring
 - Threshold evaluation
 - Pattern recognition

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- Early warning systems
- Response Coordination
 - Team collaboration
 - Resource allocation
 - Intervention timing
 - Follow-up procedures

VIII. IMPLEMENTATION GUIDELINES

Implementing AI systems in crisis support services must align with the fundamental principles that govern AI's role in society [9]. Drawing from the unified framework of beneficence, non-maleficence, autonomy, justice, and explicability, these guidelines ensure that every implementation aspect actively promotes human welfare while preventing harm.

A. Technical Requirements

The technical foundation of AI implementation demands more than mere functionality; it requires deeply integrating ethical principles into every system component. This integration ensures that technology not only performs its intended function but does so in a way that actively promotes societal good.

System Specifications reflect ethical principles through:

- Beneficence Implementation
 - Positive impact measurement systems that quantify real benefits
 - Value optimization frameworks ensuring maximum societal good
 - Benefit tracking mechanisms monitoring actual outcomes
 - Welfare enhancement tools focused on user wellbeing

The principle of non-maleficence shapes control mechanisms:

- Non-maleficence Controls
 - Harm prevention systems with proactive monitoring
 - Risk mitigation frameworks addressing potential issues
 - Safety monitoring tools providing real-time protection
 - Protection mechanisms ensuring user safety

Integration Requirements emphasize the delicate balance between system capability and human autonomy:

- Autonomy Preservation
 - User control systems that maintain human agency
 - Choice protection mechanisms ensuring user empowerment
 - Decision support frameworks that enhance rather than replace
 - Agency preservation tools protecting user independence

Justice and fairness stand at the core of system integration:

- Justice Implementation
 - Fairness assessment tools ensuring equitable service
 - Equity monitoring systems tracking access patterns
 - Bias prevention mechanisms with continuous evaluation
 - Access equality frameworks promoting universal service

Fig. 2: Implementation Success Factors [9]

B. Operational Procedures

Perhaps the most critical aspect of implementation is translating ethical principles into daily operations. Abstract principles become concrete actions that directly impact service delivery and user experience.

Training Protocols embody these principles through:

- Ethical Understanding
 - Principle awareness training that builds deep comprehension
 - Value alignment education ensures consistent application
 - Ethical decision-making frameworks for complex situations
 - Impact assessment skills development

Documentation Requirements serve as the backbone of ethical implementation:

- Principle Alignment
 - Ethics documentation tracking principle adherence
 - Decision justification records ensure transparency
 - Impact assessment records monitoring outcomes
 - Compliance verification maintaining standards

Quality Assurance Measures actively promote ethical service delivery:

- Ethical Compliance
 - Principle adherence verification through regular audits
 - Value alignment checking with continuous monitoring
 - Impact assessment tracking actual outcomes
 - Fairness evaluation ensures equitable service

IX. FUTURE DIRECTIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

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The future landscape of AI in crisis support services demands careful consideration of ethical principles and professional conduct as outlined in established guidelines [10]. The evolution of these systems must be guided by a strong moral compass, ensuring that technological advancement serves humanity's best interests while upholding professional integrity.

A. Research Opportunities

Pursuing research opportunities in AI-enabled crisis support must align with fundamental ethical principles, particularly focusing on beneficence and avoiding harm. Current gaps in the field present significant opportunities for ethically-guided innovation.

Identified Gaps encompass ethical and technical dimensions:

- Algorithmic Fairness
 - Bias detection mechanisms that ensure equitable service
 - Fair resource allocation systems
 - Inclusive design approaches
 - Ethical decision-making frameworks
- Privacy Protection
 - Advanced anonymization techniques
 - Secure data handling methods
 - Confidentiality preservation
 - User privacy safeguards

Potential Improvements focus on ethical enhancement:

- Transparency Mechanisms
 - Explainable AI implementations
 - Clear decision-making trails
 - Accountability frameworks
 - User understanding tools
- Professional Development
 - Ethical training programs
 - Competency assessments
 - Responsibility awareness
 - Moral judgment enhancement

Innovation Areas align with ethical principles:

- Responsible AI Development
 - Ethics-by-design approaches
 - Value-sensitive engineering
 - Human-centered innovation
 - Sustainable development practices
- Service Enhancement
 - Trust-building mechanisms
 - Quality assurance systems
 - User empowerment tools
 - Support optimization methods

B. Policy Recommendations

Drawing from the ACM Code of Ethics [10], policy recommendations must emphasize professional responsibility and societal impact. The framework for future development should prioritize ethical considerations while maintaining high professional standards.

Regulatory Considerations emphasize:

- Ethical Compliance
 - Professional conduct standards
 - Moral responsibility frameworks
 - Accountability measures
 - Transparency requirements
- Public Good
 - Societal benefit assessment
 - Community impact evaluation
 - Social responsibility measures
 - Public interest protection

Industry Standards must reflect:

- Professional Excellence
 - Quality benchmarks
 - Performance metrics
 - Competency requirements
 - Ethical guidelines
- Continuous Improvement
 - Regular assessments
 - Update protocols
 - Enhancement procedures
 - Innovation integration

Best Practices incorporate:

- Ethical Implementation
 - Responsible deployment
 - Fair practice guidelines
 - User protection measures
 - Privacy safeguards
- Professional Development
 - Ongoing training
 - Skills enhancement
 - Ethical awareness
 - Competency maintenance

CONCLUSION

Integrating AI in abuse helpline contact centers represents a critical advancement in crisis support services, demanding a careful balance between technological innovation and human-centered care. Throughout this analysis, The article has demonstrated that successful implementation requires a comprehensive framework addressing ethical considerations, human-AI collaboration, safety measures, regulatory compliance, emotional intelligence integration, and robust implementation guidelines. The article highlights that while AI can significantly enhance service delivery through improved efficiency, consistent monitoring, and advanced support capabilities, it must fundamentally serve to augment rather than replace human emotional intelligence and empathy. Critical success factors include rigorous privacy protection, bias mitigation, transparent operations, comprehensive staff training, and continuous quality assurance. As we look toward the future, the emphasis must remain on ethical deployment, regulatory compliance, and the maintenance of human dignity in crisis support services. The framework presented provides a foundation for organizations seeking to leverage AI's capabilities while upholding the highest standards of care and professional conduct. Continuing research, policy development, and industry collaboration will be essential to ensure that AI-enabled crisis support systems effectively serve their fundamental purpose: supporting vulnerable individuals with compassion, reliability, and unwavering ethical commitment.

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Citation: Santhosh Kumar Ganesan, (2024). Integrating Responsible AI in Abuse Helpline Contact Centers: A Framework for Ethical Implementation and Human-Centered Support. International Journal of Research in Computer Applications and Information Technology, 7(2), 1026–1042.

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✉ editor@iaeme.com